

Meta-analysis provides a framework for combining evidence across several studies to obtain a more precise and generalizable estimate of an overall effect. However, differences in study-level conditions may lead to heterogeneity in effect sizes. Meta-regression extends this framework by incorporating study-level covariates (“moderators”) to explain why effect sizes or clinical outcomes differ across studies, for example due to variation in patient age, disease stage, follow-up duration, or treatment setting. Identifying relevant moderators based on the data is crucial, yet traditional methods such as Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) often become unreliable in case of sparse data, when the number of studies is small, or when heterogeneity is high. We investigate Bayesian model selection techniques based on marginal likelihoods (or Bayes factors, BFs). Because the direct computation of marginal likelihoods can be challenging, we also consider approximation methods such as Fractional Bayes Factors (FBFs) and integrated nested Laplace approximations (INLA). We then compare these approaches with commonly used information criteria, such as the widely applicable information criterion (WAIC) or leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV). Bayesian methods (based on marginal likelihoods) do not only allow to identify a single “best fitting” model, but also provide greater interpretability as well as proper uncertainty quantification; on the other hand, such methods are often computationally challenging. Using applied examples and simulations, we compare BF, FBF, as well as corresponding median probability models (MPMs), with corrected AICs (AICc), WAICs and LOO-CV. The focus here is on the trade-off of accuracy and computational burden, and we investigate particular issues arising in the examination of interaction effects as well as applications in network meta-analysis. The aim is to provide reliable inference methods to foster rational clinical decision making.